

AGE-RELATED MORPHOLOGICAL DISTRIBUTION OF HODJKIN LYMPHOMA
TYPES IN KHOREZM REGION.

Avezov.A.U., Kadamova M.A.

Urgench branch of Tashkent Medical Academy

The medical history and outpatient card data of patients who applied to the Khorezm branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Oncology and Radiology, were diagnosed with Hodgkin lymphoma, and received complex treatment, scientific analysis of the results of morphological examinations, the archive of the pathological and histological laboratory, histological blocks of the indicated years, and the results obtained from the examination cards filled out for each patient were used.

Relevance of the problem. Hodgkin lymphoma is one of the tumor processes originating from lymphoid tissue, which has certain morphological and immunohistochemical characteristics. This type of tumor is distinguished as a separate clinical and morphological type among lymphomas, and morphological changes are of decisive importance in diagnosis. Reed-Sternberg cells and their immunophenotype are the main criteria for differentiating HL from other lymphoproliferative diseases. In terms of morphological characteristics, Hodgkin lymphoma is a type of tumor with a microscopically unique cellular composition and tissue structure. Its main morphological features are large cells with two or more nuclei and a "double-eyed" chromatin structure in the nucleus, i.e. Reed-Sternberg cells. The presence of cells is the identification of mononuclear cells, a single-nucleated form of Reed-Sternberg cells. Lymphocytes, eosinophils, histiocytes, neutrophils and plasma cells are observed in the resulting infiltrate. In some types of this tumor, elements of fibrosis, granuloma and necrosis are found.

The study included 80 people, of whom 48 (60%) were men and 32 (40%) were women. When the study participants were divided into age groups, the following were observed: in the 4-17 age group, a total of 24 (25%) patients were observed; of which 8 (5%) were observed in women and 16 (20%) in men; in the 18-34 age group, the disease was observed in 11 (13.75%) cases among men and none among women; in the 35-49 age group, a total of 20 (21.25%) patients were observed; of which 8 (6.25%) were women and 12 (15%) were men; In the 50-64 age group, the number of patients was 15 (16.25%), with 8 (10%) cases among men and 7 (6.25%) among women. In the 65-74 age group, the incidence was slightly lower, with 6 (7.5%) cases, more among women than men, with 9 (6.25%) cases, and less among men, with 1 (1.25%) patient. There were no cases among those aged 75 years and older.

Used literature.

1. Kamalova F. Sh. i dr. Epidemiological and clinical features of lymphoproliferative diseases with head and neck organ damage // *Oncohematology* . - 2021. - T. 16. – no. 3. - S. 105-117.
2. Tosheva R. S., Ismailova M. Kh., Ilkhamov D. F. The role is computer-based tomogra-fii i uzd v diagnostike zlokachestvennyx lymphoma // *INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*. - 2021. - S. 194.
3. Tillyashaykhov M.N. , Ibragimova Sh.N., Djanklich S.M., Sostoyanie onkologicheskoy pomoshchi naseleniyu Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019, Izd : "Fan" Academy of Science Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent- 2020., str. 85,

4. Ognerubov N. A., Antipova T. S. Radiation -induced sarcoma of soft tissue after radiation therapy Lymphoma Khodzhkina . Kliniche-scoe nablyudenie //Sovremennaya onkologiya. - 2022. - T. 24. – no. 3. - S. 325-330.
5. Patrakeeva V. P., Dobrodeeva L. K. Immune reactions in Hodgkin 's lymphoma // Medicine of extreme situations . - 2023. - T. 25. – no. 2. - S. 77-84.
6. Plastinina , Lyubov Vasilevna Clinical and pathomorphological characteristics of follicular lymphoma of the 3rd cytological type: autoref . Dis ... cand. Med. Nauk.- M., 2017.- 24 p.
7. Senchenko M. A. i dr. Clinical and morphological characteristics of nodular lymphoma Hodgkina with limfocytarnym preobladaniem u detey. Opyt odnogo Tsentra //Voprosy hematologii/onkologii i immunopatologii v pe-diatrii . - 2021. - T. 20. – no. 2. - S. 111-120.
8. Samanyova N. Yu. i dr. Evolutsiya lekarstvennogo lecheniya klasicheskoy lymphoma HODZKINA // Yujno-rossiyskiy onkologicheskiy zurnal. - 2022. - T. 3. – no. 3. - S. 41-47.
9. Shupletsova I. A. i dr. Clinical-pathomorphological characteristics are non- dullary lymphoma Hodzhkina with lymphoid preobladaniem v zavizimosti ot vremeni ot poyavleniya lymphadenopathy do vypolneniya biopsii //Hematologiya i transfuziologiya. - 2020. - T. 65. – no. S1. - S. 246-246.
10. Shupletsova I. A., Kovrigina A. M. Characteristics and frequency of diagnosis of variantov virus Epstein - Barr -positive lymphoma Hodzhkina with lympho-idnym preobladaniem and structural lymphoma Khodzhkina //Hematology and Transfusiology. - 2021. - T. 66. - no. 4. – S. 567-579
11. Ameli F, Zahavi Z, Kosari F , Soleimani V. The utility of PAX8 in comparison with PAX5 immunohistochemical staining in the diagnosis of Hodgkin lymphoma. //Ann Diagn Pathol . 2022 Oct;60:151974
12. Amraee A, Evazi MR, Shakeri M, et al. Efficacy of nivolumab as checkpoint inhibitor drug on survival rate of patients with relapsed/refractory classical Hodgkin lymphoma: a meta-analysis of prospective clinical study. // Clin Transl Oncol . 2019 ;21 (8):1093–1103.
13. Arlt A., von Bonin F., Rehberg T. et al. High CD206 levels in Hodgkin lymphoma-educated macrophages are linked to matrix-remodeling and lymphoma dissemination. // Mol Oncol 2020 ;14 (3):571-89.
14. Chiu WC, Chen SH, Chen BJ, Huang YL, Miserc JS, Wei CH, Lin WC. Primary pulmonary Hodgkin's lymphoma: A rare etiology mimicking pulmonary tuberculosis . // Pediatrician Neonatal . 2021 Sep ;62 (5):569-570.